

FACTORS AFFECTING TO THE ADOPTION OF SOCIAL MEDIA BY SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES (SMEs) IN SRI LANKA

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Introduction

Social media creates an online community for the people who share their activities, objectives, and interests. It has become the most popular tool in the world today (Srinivasan, Bajaj & Bhanot, 2016). Social media has become a necessity for individuals and businesses today (AlSharji et al., 2018). Many larger businesses and small businesses can gain competitive advantages and benefits by using social media. However, there are some limitations in the application of social media. Many SMEs tend to reject IT usage as they do not have enough resources to manage big IT projects, lack of IT knowledge and technical expertise (Alsharji et al., 2018; He et al., 2015). According to He et al. (2015), many businesses have faced the challenge of reaching the customers with the limited resources. As social media is cost effective and easy to use, it is a suitable way to reach large potential customers easily (Beier & Wagner, 2016). However, still the potential and the purpose of social media for small business is undiscovered by the SME owners (Ahamat et al., 2017).

The objectives of this research are (1) to identify the factors that influence Small and Medium Enterprises to adopt social media (2) to study the relationship between social media adopting factors and the adoption of social media by Small and Medium Enterprises.

Methodology

The study has used the cross-sectional quantitative approach to empirically prove the objectives. The population of this study was all the SMEs in Sri Lanka. The sample was 84 social media adopted (Facebook) SMEs in Sri Lanka selected using convenient sampling and quota sampling. The data collection was done by an online questionnaire (Google form).

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) by Davis (1989), a model which is widely used in information system research areas was employed by extending with Perceived Trust (PT). In this research, the linkage between Perceived Ease of Use (PEU) towards the Perceived Usefulness (PU) did not take in when building the conceptual model.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Below are the hypotheses that were developed for the study.

H1: Perceived usefulness (PU) has a significant influence for the adoption of social media by Sri Lankan SMEs.

H2: Perceived ease of use (PEU) has a significant influence for the adoption of social media by Sri Lankan SMEs.

H3: Perceived trust has a significant influence for the adoption of social media by Sri Lankan SMEs.

Results and Discussion

The questionnaire designed with five-point Likert scale was employed for the data gathering from the respondents. The questionnaire was adopted from previous literature by supporting the model.

Reliability and Validity Analysis

Except one item (which is greater than 0.6) all the other items were in indicator reliability. Therefore, no item was dropped in this study. All constructs were above 0.5, there is convergent validity in this study. Further discriminant validity was demonstrated.

Table 1. Hypotheses testing

Hypotheses	Path	T statistics	P-Value	Decision
H1	Perceived Usefulness -> Adoption of Social Media	4.017	0.000	Supported
H2	Perceived Ease of Use -> Adoption of Social Media	0.974	0.331	Not supported
H3	Perceived Trust -> Adoption of Social Media	1.181	0.238	Not supported

H1: Perceived usefulness has a significant influence for the adoption of social media by Sri Lankan SMEs.

The results ($P < 0.05$) suggest that SMEs in Sri Lanka will adopt social media into their business if that social media is useful for them. The finding was compatible with earlier studies. Ahamat et al. (2017) identified that a high amount of perceived usefulness results in higher levels of social media adoption by SMEs.

H2: Perceived ease of use has a significant influence for the adoption of social media by Sri Lankan SMEs.

The result ($P > 0.05$) suggests **that there is no relationship** between the ease of use and adoption of social media. The finding was not compatible with earlier studies (Ahamat et al., 2017; Beier & Wagner, 2016). Ahamat et al. (2017) identified that a high amount of perceived ease of use results in higher levels of social media adoption by SMEs.

H3: Perceived trust has a significant influence for the adoption of social media by Sri Lankan SMEs.

The results ($P > 0.05$) suggest **that there is no relationship** between the trust and adoption of social media. The finding was not compatible with earlier studies. Ahamat et al. (2017) identified that higher levels of perceived trust results in higher levels of social media adoption by SMEs.

Conclusion

Three hypotheses were tested to find out the factors affecting the adoption of social media by SMEs in Sri Lanka and to find the connection between the factors and the use of social media platforms by SMEs in Sri Lanka. According to the study, SMEs will adopt social media if they find that it is useful. The ease of using social media and having trust for social media does not affect the adoption of social media by SMEs.

The theoretical perspective of this study is concerned with factors for the use of social media platforms by SMEs in Sri Lanka. The practical

importance of this study is that the decision makers of SMEs can combine technology for their business by adding more value to customers' experiences.

Limitation

There are some limitations in this study. The sample of this study was taken in the Sri Lankan context which cannot be generalized. The study is cross sectional, but the effect of social media may not be static. The study was done with Facebook platform and not in depth.

Recommendation

Future research can be conducted using the data in other countries and by having a longitude survey to examine the effect over time. It can be conducted to address the need for more complex models of technology adoption with respect to social media applications in SMEs. The study can be done using in depth surveys.

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